

Recommendations for Following a Low-Antioxidant Diet for Two Days Before the Study Visit

Restricted	Moderated	Allowed
FOOD		
Whole cereals and corn	Vegetables: garlic, onion, turnip, eggplant (with peel), artichoke, iceberg lettuce	Refined cereals (white rice, pasta...)
Cured cheese	Soy and derivatives (tofu...)	Meat
Yolk	Broad beans	Fish
Green leafy vegetables (spinach, Swiss chard, watercress...)	Fruits: pineapple, avocado, lemon, kiwi, banana	Skimmed dairy products (milk, yogurt...)
Vegetables: carrot, tomato, broccoli, cabbages, pepper, leek, pumpkin, asparagus, green beans, beet, sweet potato	Olive oil	Egg white
Fruits: orange, tangerine, grapefruit, red fruits (strawberries, blueberries, blackberries, raspberries...), grape pomegranate, plum, papaya, cantaloupe, persimmon, peach		Vegetables: eggplant (without peel), celery, zucchini, cauliflower, radish, potato, cucumber
Olives		Mushrooms
Green peas		Fruits: apple (without peel), pear (without peel), pineapple in syrup, figs
Nuts (almonds, walnuts...)		Legumes: white beans, chickpeas, lentils
Aromatic herbs (parsley, coriander, oregano...)		
Spices (turmeric, paprika...)		
Mustard		
Algae		
Cocoa		
BEVERAGES		
Infusions and teas	Coffee (maxim 1 coffee/day)	Water
Beer	Spirits	Carbonated water
Wine, cava, or cider		Soda
Cocoa beverage		Chicken or fish broth (without vegetables)
Fruit juices		
Vegetable beverage (soymilk, almond milk...)		